

ESI-MS Report

University
of Basel

Department of
Chemistry

Sample Information

Acquired by	: System Administrator
Date Acquired	: 13.02.2020 13:11:03
Sample Name	: ARN038
Sample ID	: ARN038
Data File	: ARN038_ARN038_001.lcd
Method File	: Only MS Autosampler.lcm
Original Method File	: Only MS Autosampler.lcm
Report Format File	: Fabian_Layout_NEW_3.lsr
Tuning File	: 190624.lct
Processed by	: System Administrator
Date Processed	: 13.02.2020 13:14:04

Method

<<Header>>

Generated	: 27.03.2019 11:36:14
Modified	: 13.02.2020 13:08:27

<<MS Parameter>>

Initial Valve Position	: -
--Segment 1 Event 1--	
Start Time	: 0.00 min
End Time	: 3.00 min
Acquisition Mode	: Profile
Polarity	: Positive
Event Time	: 0.50 sec
Detector Voltage	: +1.10 kV
Start m/z	: 100.00
End m/z	: 1000.00
Scan Speed	: 1875 u/sec
Interface Volt.	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
DL Volt.	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
--Segment 1 Event 2--	
Start Time	: 0.00 min
End Time	: 3.00 min
Acquisition Mode	: Profile
Polarity	: Negative
Event Time	: 0.50 sec
Detector Voltage	: +1.10 kV
Start m/z	: 100.00
End m/z	: 500.00
Scan Speed	: 834 u/sec
Interface Volt.	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
DL Volt.	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	: Use the Data in the Tuning File

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan

Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
MassPeaks:9
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.017-0.117(3-15) Base Peak:897.16(4639259)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.517-1.900(183-229) Segment 1 - Event 1

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan Zoomed View

Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
MassPeaks:9
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.017-0.117(3-15) Base Peak:897.16(4639259)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.517-1.900(183-229) Segment 1 - Event 1

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan Zoomed View

Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
MassPeaks:9
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.017-0.117(3-15) Base Peak:897.16(4639259)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.517-1.900(183-229) Segment 1 - Event 1

MS Spectrum Negative mode
Line#:2 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
MassPeaks:2
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.025-0.125(4-16) Base Peak:312.83(568318)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.525-1.908(184-230) Segment 1 - Event 2

MS Spectrum Negative mode Zoomed view
Line#:2 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
MassPeaks:2
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.025-0.125(4-16) Base Peak:312.83(568318)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.525-1.908(184-230) Segment 1 - Event 2

MS Spectrum Negative mode Zoomed view
Line#:2 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
MassPeaks:2
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.025-0.125(4-16) Base Peak:312.83(568318)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.525-1.908(184-230) Segment 1 - Event 2

